

UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF THE TWITTER BAN IN NIGERIA: A SCHOLARLY REVIEW

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Essien Oku EssienDepartment of Mass Communication
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The free nature of the social media has often resulted in their misuse. These media have grown beyond censorship and control and so, users –especially the youths sometimes use them negatively. Social media have at some point been used to mobilise citizens for mass protests in different parts of the world. One of such protests was the #EndSARS protest in Nigeria which led to loss of lives and massive destruction of properties that left indelible marks in the footprints of time. To forestall such occurrences, the federal government of Nigeria which had become critical of social media use for anti-government protestations in one of her moves to regulate the social media placed a ban on the use of Twitter in Nigeria. This paper presents a scholarly review of the causes and consequences of the Twitter ban in Nigeria. The authors argue that the ban on Twitter had tremendous implications for the development and sustainability of free speech which is a key component of democracy. The paper further examines the unintended consequences of the ban on Nigeria as a whole. It concludes that the Twitter ban rather than stifle free speech, gave users alternative means of expression which attracted negative consequences to the credibility of the present administration. It further strengthened the growing critical mass of Nigeria's digital constituency that has become the voice of emancipation of the populace.

Keywords: *Hashtags, EndSARS, Twitter, Protests, Censorship, Social Media, Campaign*

Introduction

Technological innovations and the ever-changing complex nature of societies in the world have revolutionized the way and manner in which information gathering and dissemination is carried out. Citizens have taken advantage of the opportunities provided by modern technologies to stay abreast with what goes on around them. The internet is one of the biggest technological revolutions and a significant proportion of the world's population have access to it. The use of technologies associated with the internet has brought about efficient, interactive, cost-effective, and convenient media for sharing vital information and opinions among people. One of such media is Twitter –an online news and social networking platform that allows people communicate with short messages called tweets. Tweeting is the act of posting short messages on Twitter with the hope that the tweets are useful and interesting to someone in the social space. Twitting is synonymous with microblogging, as it promotes interaction and public participation in topical issues in the society. The supple and interactive nature of Twitter has presented numerous opportunities for the public to interact on a variety of issues. It has been used by business owners and corporate organisations to publicise their products and services. To small and medium-scale enterprises, it has served as a platform for reaching out to customers and target audiences, in order to promote their businesses. Twitter has been used by the masses for reasons suitable to them, most notably to express opinions and freedom of speech on societal and political matters.

Twitter has been used in different climes to mobilise people for mass actions and this has accorded it the status of an emancipatory medium. In Nigeria for instance, the #EndSARS protest started in 2017 as a Twitter campaign against the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) of the Nigerian Police. According to Inyang and Essien (2021), the protest sought the disbandment of that unit by the Nigerian government. By October 2020, the hash tag culminated into a mass protest in the country and by that time, 48 million tweets bearing the #EndSARS had accumulated on Twitter. The climax of the protest claimed the lives of about seventy eight protesters at the Lekki tollgate in Lagos, Nigeria. The Lekki tollgate massacre according to Inyang and Essien

(2021) was greeted with untold mayhem let loose by aggrieved citizens which resulted in the loss of more lives and wanton destruction of properties. The protest however, led to the dissolution of SARS and subsequent creation of the Special Weapons and Tactics (SWAT) unit of the Nigerian Police.

Issues with social media use in Nigeria

Inyang and Essien (2021) have reasoned that social media are very powerful when it comes to circulation of information, values and sentiments. This is in line with the thoughts of Inyang and Edem (2020), who argued that social media provide platforms for interactions that can stimulate new and fading thoughts, images, traditions and uniqueness due to their potent nature and that they can be used to effectively mobilize and demobilize people. Salaudeen and Lawal (2019) also added that the acceptance and suitability of social media among youths have gone beyond imagination and control. Social media like Twitter create avenues for issues to be brought to the fore, rouse public opinion and allow individuals and corporate bodies to speak, express and make public without unnecessary restriction, they help to preserve social harmony by revealing social ills like corruption, bad governance, insurgency, etc. and discourages other bad conducts (Inyang & Essien, 2021).

The Nigerian government had long held concerns over the use of Twitter in the country, arguing that Twitter like every other social medium is loose and porous, and that considering the volume and nature of information that passes through it, it needs to be socially responsible. Social responsibility according to Inyang and Essien (2021) suggests permitting free flow of information, but the thrust of such information should be brought to public sphere and the media which carry them should accept any responsibility arising from public interference or professional self-regulations or both. The #EndSARS protest that resulted in loss of lives and wanton destruction of properties, as well as democratic disorder began on Twitter in 2017 and escalated in 2020 when it gathered 48 million tweets in just ten days. #EndSARS updates were made and organized on the trace of exaggeration as a result of the misery, rage and feeling of discontent that consumed the atmosphere. While certain content creators upheld a singular position in exhibiting evidence regarding the professed poor policing, others grabbed the opportunity to expand their contents and as well spread their scope towards economic recession and bad governance (Inyang & Essien, 2021).

Resulting from the outcome of the Lekki toll gate killings of October 2020, and the perceived involvement of the Nigerian government in the massacre, the hash tag campaign suddenly switched from #EndSARS, #EndPoliceBrutality –to- #ImpeachBuhari. While the previous hash tags were still used in online campaign posts, the latter seemed to raise another wave of protest as was seen online as ‘Revolution 2020’. The Nigerian government had since then floated the idea of social media regulation on different occasions prior to the ban on Twitter.

The ban on Twitter in Nigeria

From the 5th of June 2021 to the 13th of January 2022, the federal government of Nigeria officially banned Twitter and restricted it from operating in Nigeria. This ban ensued after Twitter deleted tweets made by Nigeria’s president Muhammadu Buhari and went ahead to suspend him for warning the Igbos of Southeastern Nigeria of a repeat of the 1967 Biafra civil war due to the continuing insurgency in the region.

The government of Nigeria stated that the removal of the presidents tweets was just one of the factors that led to the ban on Twitter. It contended that ban was prompted by a series of problems emanating from the use of social media in Nigeria, as they were used for misinformation and to spread fake news that had real world

violent consequences. The government made reference to the tenacious use of social media for activities that are capable of undermining Nigeria's corporate existence.

The ban on Twitter was greeted with mixed reactions, while it was condemned by civil society organisations like Amnesty International, the British, Canadian and Swedish diplomatic missions in Nigeria, and the European Union, the Socio-economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) and the Nigerian Bar Association initiated court processes to challenge the ban in court. A former United States president Donald Trump however, congratulated the Nigerian government and urged other responsible governments to emulate Nigeria. The ban lasted for about seven months.

Consequences of the Twitter ban in Nigeria

Consequent upon the Twitter ban in Nigeria, Twitter users turned to virtual private networks as alternatives to access Twitter. People were forced to use these encrypted connections to evade the ban and to continue using Twitter remotely without necessarily allowing people to spy on their activities. Since the traffic was encrypted between their devices and the network, traffic remained private as it travelled. A user could work outside an office environment and still securely connect to a corporate network. To log into a Twitter account using a virtual private network, all a user needed to do was to sign up with a VPN provider, log onto the service first, before connecting to the internet. Once that was done, nobody could monitor their activities as VPN providers would encrypt private data and scramble them in such a way that hackers, whether government agencies or businesses would not be able to review the activities of the users. Paquette (2021), noted that the demand for these firewall-circumventing apps jumped by more than 1,400 percent over the weekend of the suspension.

The ban on Twitter in Nigeria also brought about unintended negative publicity as Nigerian based Twitter users devised other subtle means of accessing the Twitter site. They would download the mobile application and use it with wrong identity and a false nationality option. What this did was to allow residents of their choice countries access to their tweets, this in turn made information about Nigeria popular in other countries far away and the news feeds did not portray a favourable image of Nigeria. The information that the Nigerian government was trying to suppress was liberally spread, farther than they would have gone if Twitter was fully operational in Nigeria.

Using these virtual private networks also came with several security risks for users. Users had little if any guarantees about the corresponding security and privacy settings, and perhaps no practical knowledge about the entities accessing their mobile traffic.

Ikram, Vallina-Rodriguez, Seneviratne. Karfer and Paxson (2020) report that there are several instances of VPN apps that expose users to serious privacy and security vulnerabilities, such as use of insecure VPN tunneling protocols, as well as IPv6 and DNS traffic leakage. They also report on a number of apps actively performing TLS interception. Of particular concern are instances of apps that inject JavaScript programs for tracking, advertising, and for redirecting e-commerce traffic to external partners.

Beyond the social implications, there were a lot of legal and economic consequences. Anym (2020) argued that millions of people across Nigeria, especially the youth, were denied access to free flow of information, while Enwang (2021) argued that Nigeria's constitution and the international human rights law, as set in the

Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression and access to information and provide that any restriction to this right must be justifiable in a democratic society.

Article 19 of the United Nations Declaration on Human Rights states that:

Everyone shall have the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds through any media and regardless of frontiers.

Article 19 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights again, allows States to guarantee the right to freedom of expression, encompassing the right to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas off all kinds through any media and regardless of frontiers. The African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights and the African Commission Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression in Africa also hold these views strongly. Even the 199 constitution in section 39 subsections (1) and (2) stipulates that:

Every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression including the freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference (2) without prejudice to subsection (1) of this section, every person shall be entitled to own, establish and operate any medium for the dissemination of information, ideas and opinion.

It was on the strengths of these that Governor Samuel Ortom of Benue State posited that the ban on Twitter was a ploy to distract Nigerians from the Federal Government's failure to address insecurity. The Governor described the ban as illegal, suppression of fundamental rights of Nigerians and a gag on social media. (Orji & Ejemba, 2021).

Many Nigerians also argued that the ban on Twitter had affected businesses maximally as many youths used twitter and other social media to advance their career. The ban also created wide gaps as many business owners used Twitter to reach out to their customers. Although some people resorted to the used of VPNs and other subtle means to promote their businesses on Twitter, most of their followers (customers) could not manipulate this medium like they did. Nwokoma (2021) argued that the ban on Twitter in Nigeria had significant implications on tax income, influencers, freelancers, startups and SMEs. Hudley, Bishi and Grossman (2021) posited that the Twitter ban was going to cause a serious damage on the economy, as many Nigerians relied on Twitter to support their work. Sikhakhane (2021) noted that most of the 39 million Nigerians who use Twitter, used it for business and networking, and that the ban was going to affect the ability of these category of people to make a decent living, and this would inturn affect the foreign investments in Nigeria's technology sector.

Conclusion

The ban on Twitter in Nigeria was instituted by the Federal Government for fear of a repeat of what happened during the EndSARS protest, where many lives were lost and valuables destroyed. The ban however, affected the lives of millions of Nigerians negatively, as it infringed upon their rights of freedom to hold opinions and to express them through any medium of their choice. It also brought about untold hardship as many businesses could not run smoothly, causing loss of revenue. The ban brought out the ingenuity of Nigerians as they sought for alternative ways to continue using Twitter in spite of the ban to carry out their day to day tasks. These

alternative ways did not come without their implications, one of which was unintended negative publicity that was generated as a result of using false location belts by Twitter users to evade the ban. The cruel approach of the government, even though widely criticized by Nigerians yielded some sort of positive results, as Twitter now has physical presence in Nigeria and is willing to regulate the activities of its users to forestall breakdown of law and order as in the case of the EndSARS protest.

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